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FEDERALISM AND RESOURCE CONTROL IN NIGERIA: CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS

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Abstract: *Federalism and the clamour for resource control have remained two issues of contentious in contemporary Nigeria. This paper examined the complex relationship between federalism and resource control. It explores how the centralization of resource control contradicts the principles of true federalism and contributes to regional tensions in the country, particularly in the oil rich Niger Delta region. The paper offers a theoretical overview of the current structure, evaluates the socio-political and economic impact of resource centralization and proposes policy recommendations for achieving a more equitable and sustainable federal system. To generate data for the study, secondary sources of information and interdisciplinary approach were employed. In the analysis, the qualitative approach was adopted. The findings revealed that the current federal system in Nigeria lacks true fiscal federalism and that restructuring resource control can enhance peace, unity and national development. The study recommended amendments of the 1999 constitution that will take natural resources from the Exclusive to the Concurrent or Residual list. It also recommended that the derivation percentage should be increased beyond 13% to reflect adequate compensation to host communities and the creation of a Sovereign Resource Control Commission to oversee fair and equitable distribution of resources, the commission would ensure that communities benefits directly. The paper also recommended a bold Political Will to implement constitutional amendments and restructure the federal system in a way that balances autonomy with peace, unity and development.*

Introduction

Very few national issues in contemporary Nigeria have profound discourse than true

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federalism and resource control since independence in 1960. As a matter of fact, never in the history of Nigerian evolution as an independent nation has it been so helplessly and almost hopelessly entangled in the contradiction of its being. This development has manifested in several ways some of which include the clamour for resource control, inter-ethnic wrangling, and socio-political crises, particularly in resource rich oil Niger Delta region.

The contradiction between Nigeria's federalism and its centralized resource governance lies at the heart of many socio-political crises in the South-South or oil rich region of Nigeria. The sense of alienation and underdevelopment experienced by these communities has fueled agitation for fiscal autonomy over natural resources and has occasionally resulted in violent confrontations, including militant insurgency.

It is true that the independence constitution of 1960 and the republican constitution of 1963 enshrined some principles of fiscal federalism and elements of resource control in the light of the level of regions enjoyed. Sadly, in the course of our political journey, these constitutions were repealed, modified and even suspended by the ruling military dictators. However, the return of democracy in 1999 and the unsolved developmental issues that the oil rich Niger

Delta region has successively experienced; there has been continuous agitation for the institutionalization of resource control and the practice of true federalism in Nigeria.

The independence constitution of 1960 and the republican constitution of 1963 granted greater fiscal autonomy to the regions, and also empowered regions to compete with each other. The recent agitation for justice and fairness in the treatment of the Niger Delta region has brought to fore the demand for resource control. The agitation has been misunderstood by Nigerians; those rooting for resource control do not seek the exclusive control and ownership of petroleum resources and other natural resources by the states. The agitation is rather, built upon the doctrine of fairness that states should have a fair stake in the exploration of natural resources in their territories.

This paper seeks to explore the historical trajectory of federalism and resource control in Nigeria, interrogate the legal and institutional structures that underpin the current arrangement, assess the socio-political and economic consequences of centralized resource control, and explore alternative models that could foster a more just and efficient federation. The main problem this study addresses is the paradox of a federal system that denies its constituent units effective control over resources. The guiding research question

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is: can Nigeria achieve sustainable peace, unity and development without restructuring its approach to resource control? By providing answers to this and related questions, the paper aims to contribute to the ongoing discourse on restructuring and the search for an equitable federal system in Nigeria.

Conceptual Clarification

The word federalism comes from the Latin word foedus. The Latin word foedus refers to a treaty or an agreement. According to Okolo (2011), federalism is a system where federal and regional (state) governments are present and each has its own set of powers and functions. For Karl (1968), federalism means that both the federal and regional (state) governments are restricted to their own areas and should not interfere with each other.

Federalism is a system of governance where power and duties are divided by a constitution between the central authority and the smaller political units. In Nigeria, the system of federalism has become very centralized, mainly when it comes to managing natural resources. Thus, the USA constitution focuses more on the states, whereas Canada's constitution gives more power to the central government. The Indian constitution, however, divides legislative power and authority between the centre and the states by listing them in the Union list, State list and Concurrent list.

Resource control can be defined as the right of the federating units, states or regions to control the natural resources within their territories and derives a substantial share of revenue from them. Since crude oil was discovered in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria, the issue of who controls the resources has become a major problem in Nigerian federalism. Odje (2000) believes that federalism and resource control complement each other; resource control is a key feature of a true federal system of governance. To Azaiki (2003), resource control is an important economic theory because land, labour, capital and entrepreneurship are considered factors of production in federalism. It means that the regions in a federation can mainly manage their natural resources and they are expected to contribute toward the maintenance of common services at the central government.

Nigeria experienced this until the military took over in 1966 and federalism was weakened under the military administration. The regions lost their independence and a strong central government was formed, with the states that replaced them becoming dependent on the central government. Oil was becoming more important than cocoa, groundnut and palm oil when the military took over.

Federalism and Resource Control in Nigeria

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Nigeria currently has a federal government, 36 states, FCT and 774 local governments. Prior to colonization, indigenous governance systems respected community based control of local resources. The colonial administration, however introduced centralized control mechanisms aimed at facilitating resource extraction for imperial benefit, laying the foundation for federal imbalances with Sir Arthur Richards constitution of 1946. In 1960 when Nigeria gained independence, she was composed of regions with considerable autonomy over internal affairs, including fiscal matters. The 1960 and 1963 constitutions upheld a derivation principle that allowed regions to retain up to 50% of the revenue generated from their resources. Sadly, the military government of Gen. Yakubu Gowon abolished regional control and placed resource governance under federal authority. The period ushered in a new federal system that could be ascribed as "cat and mouse federalism". This structure accelerated the struggle over control of the center as whosoever contains the centre takes control of all sections of the state. This resulted to the Nigeria Biafra war. This war was purely a mere expression of greed and dominance.

The federal system after the civil war strained the relationship exiting amongst ethnic groups in Nigeria. The issue of control of resources now becomes the sole responsibility of the federal or

the central government. The Petroleum Act of 1969 and Land use Act of 1978 further compounded the problem. The Petroleum Act of 1969 entrenched federal control over natural resources and the Land Act of 1978 nationalized land ownership, further eroding state and local authority. The Niger Delta people at this juncture perceived the majority groups as their greatest enemy, because during the pre-oil economy, the regions control their resources but when oil became the main stay of the economy, the Nigerian state controls all.

Okowa (2007) stated that the contemporary Nigeria depends on the exploitation and expropriation of the resources of the powerless minorities of the Niger Delta region for onward transfer in favor of the ethnic majors. This is akin to a colonial enterprise; hence the inevitability of the brutality of man against man and the environment in the process of resource exploitation and expropriation as is being witnessed in the Niger Delta. Okowa (2007) further described the current federal system as "cat and mouse federalism". A system in which the cat dictates rules of life, it is impossible for the mouse to survive let alone develop. This arrangement has accelerated the pace of agitation for resource control in the oil rich Niger Delta region.

Legal and Constitutional Frame Work

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The legal instruments that currently govern resource control in the country are the 1999 constitution and the landmark case, Attorney general of the federation vs. the Attorney general of Abia state (2002). The 1999 constitution place oil and mineral resources under the exclusive legislative list, which granted exclusive rights to the federal or central government. Section 162 of the 1999 constitution introduces the derivation principle but limits it to a minimum of 13% of revenue derived from petroleum and other natural resources, which is a sharp contrast to earlier constitutional arrangements.

Additionally, the judicial pronouncement on resource control, particularly the case between Attorney general of the federation verses the Attorney general of Abia state (2002) reaffirmed federal ownership of offshore oil resources. This ruling of the Supreme Court, have exacerbated tensions and calls for constitutional amendments.

The Resource Control Debate

Most Nigerians have not fully understood the debate about resource control. The study highlights that the proponents for resource control do not want the region to have exclusive ownership and control of petroleum and other natural resources. The movement is based on the belief that communities should have a

stronger interest in exploring minerals found within their domains.

They argue that resource control is essential for addressing environmental degradation, local underdevelopment, and the historical injustice of revenue centralization. They cited examples of oil spills, gas flaring, and poor infrastructure in resource-rich communities as justification for a more decentralized resource governance model.

Opponents, often from other regions of the country, especially from Northern Nigeria express fears that resource control could lead to fiscal imbalances, exacerbate inequality, or even threaten the nation's unity, peace and development. They concluded that the central control promotes redistribution and national development.

Socio-Political and Economic Implications of Centralized Resource Governance

Socially, the Nigeria's resource governance model has contributed to wide spread unrest and the emergence of militancy in the oil rich Niger Delta region. Most Militant groups like the Movement for the Emancipation of the Niger Delta (MEND) and the Niger Delta Avengers emerged in response to perceived exploitation, leading to economic sabotage, including attacks on oil facilities and installations in the oil rich region. Politically,

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the tension around the centralization of resources has undermined national cohesion. Notable southern leaders, particularly from the oil rich region have called for restructuring, while northern elites have resisted changes to the status quo, creating a north-south divide in national discourse and dialogue.

Economically, the dependency on federally allocated funds has stifled creativity and self-reliance among many states. The 'fiscal laziness' syndrome has led to poor internal revenue generation and excessive reliance on federal disbursements. Oil producing states argue that they receive an inadequate share of the wealth they produce, which further fuel discontent. Even as states like Akwa Ibom and Rivers have used derivation funds effectively for infrastructure and human capital development, pointing to the potential benefits of true resource control.

Comparative Perspectives

During the first republic, Nigeria's federalism was not the same as the post-military system, where the three and later four regions were completely independent federating units. Every region had a premier as its leader and made its own laws and constitution. The native authorities had their own police and the Nigerian police were under the control of the federal government. Every region also had its own symbol of authority. No region was

completely dependent on the central government for its finances and other needs; each region was self-sufficient and wealthy.

Sadly, from January 15, 1966 to October 1, 1979, Nigeria was ruled by a military government. The military leaders played a role in shaping the country's political and administrative systems. The first change was decree 34 of 1966 which was issued by the first military head of state, Major General Aguiyi Ironsi and it made Nigeria a unitary state. Because of the political crisis and the serious threats to the federation, Gen. Ironsi believed that a unitary government with a strong centre was what Nigeria needed at that time. When the military left power on October 1, 1979, they had managed to change the nature of the federation to address the nation's long-standing issues of fear and domination. The centre grew strong and the states grew weak and this situation has not changed. Federal system in Canada, Australia and the United States are totally different from what Nigeria currently operates. In Canada, provinces have ownership rights over natural resources, and fiscal equalization mechanisms ensure national equity. In Australia, a combination of state control and national coordination has enabled balanced development. Also the United States model allows individual states to benefit significantly from resource found within their borders, promoting investment in local

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infrastructure and education. These models show that decentralized control, when combined with accountability and redistribution frame works, can promote both national unity and development.

It is important that Nigeria should learn from these examples by customizing similar models to its diverse and complex environment.

Policy Recommendations

There is need for a comprehensive reform strategy. First, the paper recommends constitutional amendments to move natural resources from the Exclusive to the Concurrent or Residual list, granting states greater autonomy. Secondly, the derivation should be increased beyond 13% percentage to reflect adequate compensation to host communities and region.

The paper also recommends creation of a Sovereign Resource Control Commission to oversee fair and equitable distribution of resources and ensure that communities benefit directly. Additionally, the paper calls for a bold political will to implement constitutional amendments that would reorganize the federal system in a way that balances autonomy with peace, unity and development.

Conclusion

True federalism means that each state or region in a federating unit is given a lot of freedom to handle its own affairs. The main focus of the

resource control debate in Nigeria is to clarify the basis of the contract of the Federalism and resource control. The study reaffirms that the current federal arrangement in Nigeria is structurally skewed against resource-providing states and is unsustainable for long term peace and development. Without genuine fiscal federalism and meaningful reforms in resource control, peace and national unity will remain elusive. Okumagba (2002) is convinced that when resource control is put into practice, it will lead to more competition and efforts to develop. The study has examined the concepts of true federalism and resource control in Nigeria as they influence the oil rich Niger Delta region of the country.

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